

A Rapid Detection Method of Plasmid DNA from COVID-19 mRNA Vaccines for Quality

Control

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Abstract

Despite the rapid development of SARS-CoV-2 mRNA vaccines to combat the Coronavirus infectious disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic, vaccine hesitancy has gained traction as the pandemic continues. Among the hot issues related to the COVID-19 mRNA vaccines, DNA contamination has cast doubt on the quality of the product and may have undermined public trust. Here, we report a simple method to detect residual replication-competent plasmid DNA that is present in mRNA vaccines as impurities. Using 4 vials of experimental mRNA vaccines, we found two out of four vials of experimental mRNA vaccines contained residual plasmid DNA that transforms *E. coli* cells. We subsequently applied our method to assess 2 separate lots of Pfizer COVID-19 mRNA vaccines and found no replication-competent plasmid DNA. However, these authorized vaccines do contain residual DNA to a level that exceeds 10 ng per dose. Our results suggest close monitoring of DNA impurity may aid the buildup of public trust in mRNA vaccines.

Introduction

The revolution in messenger RNA (mRNA) technology has enabled the rapid development of coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) mRNA vaccine (1). The award of 2023 Nobel Prize in Medicine to Drs. Katalin Karikó and Drew Weissman for their work of modifying mRNA to make it a therapeutic—enabling a platform catapulted the technology into the limelight. COVID-19 mRNA vaccines are made of an antigen-encoding messenger RNA encapsulated into lipid nanoparticles (2). The mRNA is transcribed from a DNA plasmid *in vitro* by T7 RNA polymerase and then purified after DNase I digestion to remove the original plasmid DNA (pDNA) (Figure 1). The purified mRNAs are subsequently formulated to obtain a lipid envelope. The mRNA-based vaccines are easy to manufacture and update. Upon administering, the mRNA is translated into the spike protein of the severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2), inducing anti-Spike antibodies and hence giving our immune system a head start over the virus. Despite millions of lives being saved, the mRNA vaccine is not perfect just as all other medical products. One critique of the COVID-19 mRNA vaccine is that there may be DNA present in the vaccine and some even associate mRNA vaccines with possibility of inducing genetic mutations in vaccinees (3). Questions like this, if not addressed, may greatly influence the receptiveness of the mRNA vaccine by the public (4-7).

By design, mRNA does not integrate into human chromosomal DNA, thus eliminates the possibility of inducing mutations in host DNA. The manufacturing of the mRNA vaccines, however, does involve the template pDNA because the flow of genetic information follows the Central Dogma, i.e., from DNA to RNA, and to protein. Despite extensive efforts, it is

impossible to completely remove all DNA impurities from the final product (8, 9). In other words, trace amount of pDNA is expected to be found in the COVID-19 mRNA vaccines as impurities. For quality control purpose, it is reasonable to set an allowable DNA limit in mRNA vaccines. However, current recommended limits (<10 ng/dose, length<200 bp), which are frequently cited in literatures, are set for continuous cell line-derived DNA by the World Health Organization and adopted by U.S. and European regulatory agencies (10-12). A few recent studies reported that the licensed Pfizer and Moderna mRNA vaccines may contain higher amounts of DNA impurities (13-15).

Compared to smaller DNA fragments, which will undergo subsequent degradation once being taken up by human cells, those larger DNA pieces with genetic elements that enable active replication (replicative or replication-competent) are potentially more harmful. To this end, we designed experiments to examine whether there is residual DNA present in COVID-19 mRNA vaccines that transform *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*) cells. We further characterized the amount and size of DNA fragments from various sources mRNA vaccines.

Results

A simple strategy to detect replication-competent DNA in mRNA vaccines

First, we designed a strategy to quickly quantify the number of undigested or linearized near full-length pDNA in the mRNA vaccine. Shown in Figure 2, undigested pDNA can be readily transformed into *E. coli* cells and form antibiotics-resistant colonies. Linearized pDNA, depending on whether it carries the bacterial replication origin and the antibiotics resistance marker, may be ligated into a circular DNA that can be transformed into competent *E. coli* cells for enumeration. Because mRNA manufacturing includes a DNase I treatment step that would in theory cleave plasmid DNA into much smaller fragments that are not transformable, the presence of transformable DNA, i.e., replication-competent DNA in *E. coli* cells, would be a strong indicator for inefficient pDNA removal and hence poor product purity. To test the feasibility of this method, we extracted DNA from an experimental mRNA vaccine (50 µg) containing the XBB.1.5 Spike protein coding sequence (Fig. 3). The concentrations of the DNA (in 30 µl), determined by a NanoDrop Spectrophotometer, are in the range of 10-100 nanograms per microliter. The presence of DNA is confirmed by agarose gel electrophoresis with the majority DNA migrating around 100 bp. We subsequently performed ligation using T4 DNA ligase and transformed the ligated product into chemically prepared DH5α cells. Our first trial yielded only one colony on Ampicillin (Amp)-containing LB plate (Fig. 3A). Interestingly, DNA extracted from the colony-derived culture revealed a size slightly over 2 kb (Fig. 3B), which contains only a portion of the original plasmid (Amp⁺) as revealed by Sanger sequencing (Fig. 3C).

Detection of replication-competent DNA from biosimilar mRNA vaccines

Next, we extracted DNA from a Moderna biosimilar (5 μg) and a Pfizer biosimilar (5 μg) mRNA vaccine in addition to our experimental mRNA vaccine (50 μg). Once again, DNA was readily detected by gel electrophoresis and concentrations ranged from 10-100 ng/ μl (30 μl in total) (Fig. 4A&B). After ligated DNA was transformed into *E. coli* cells, we only detected two colonies from the Pfizer biosimilar vaccine-derived DNA. Both colonies were culturable (Fig. 4C), and DNA extracted from the colonies-derived cultures consisted of 2 or 3 fragments of different size (Fig. 4D).

DNA impurity in Pfizer mRNA vaccines

Having established this method, we conducted another experiment using two lots of commercial Pfizer mRNA vaccine (Lot PAA194854, monovalent; and PAA184098, bivalent). Three separate vials of mRNA from each lot were used for DNA extraction by three different operators (Fig. 5A). Once again, agarose gel electrophoresis confirmed the presence of small DNA fragments (around 100 bp) (Fig. 5B). After transformation, ligated product did not yield any colony (Fig. 5C). These results support a complete removal of replication-competent pDNA from the Pfizer mRNA lots. Because the resolution of agarose gel electrophoresis is fairly low for smaller DNA fragments, we submitted DNA samples for size analysis on an Agilent 2100 Bioanalyzer. Shown in Figure 5D&E, all six samples displayed a prominent band close to the 35-bp DNA ladder with very little product above this size. To quantify the amount of DNA in the commercial mRNA vaccines, we measured the DNA concentration from six trial samples and then calculated the amount of DNA in 30 μg mRNA (an equivalent of one human dose). Because NanoDrop spectrophotometer detects DNA of all forms, we also measured the DNA using Qubit dsDNA HS assay. Shown in Table 1, the amount of DNA, detected by NanoDrop, from an equivalent of

one human dose mRNA vaccine falls into the range of several thousand nanograms. The amount of DNA, quantified by the more accurate Qubit dsDNA HS assay, ranges from 40-131 nanograms. Overall, we conclude that there is significant amount of DNA from the Pfizer mRNA vaccine equivalent to one human dose (Fig. 6). However, the DNA is nearly all composed of small fragments of around 35 bp in length. Once again, this finding is consistent with a fully executed DNase I treatment of the commercial mRNA vaccine.

Discussion

Not more than 10 ng/dose (<10 ng/dose) is a limit of cell substrate derived residual DNA recommended by the WHO guideline for parenteral viral vaccines produced using continuous non-tumorigenic cell lines (https://cdn.who.int/media/docs/default-source/biologicals/cell-substrates/cells.final.mtgrep.ik.26_sep_07.pdf?sfvrsn=3db7d37a_3&download=true). The residual DNA in the COVID-19 mRNA vaccines, however, is derived from digested and undigested plasmid DNA (pDNA) template from which mRNA is transcribed. As the pDNA template does not contain eukaryotic promoters or replication origins, the potential harm caused by the pDNA fragments may be lower than that from cellular DNA. Nonetheless, establishing a limit for pDNA in each dose of the mRNA vaccine will ensure manufacturing consistency.

In this study, residual DNA was detected from six vials of two different lots of Pfizer COVID-19 mRNA vaccines. The estimated amount of residual DNA in one human dose appears to be 6 to 470 times of 10 ng. This amount is slightly less than reported by another group (16). Different DNA extraction and quantification methods may account for the discrepancy. In support, we noted a significant difference between the amounts of DNA measured by NanoDrop or Qubit dsDNA HS assay. Nanodrop is a spectrometer that measures DNA concentration based on UV absorbance, which does not distinguish DNA or RNA. It is also easily affected by free nucleotides, salts, and organic compounds. Although we performed DNA extraction using a commercial kit that includes RNase in the reagent, we are unable to verify the extent of removal of RNA. Hence, it is possible that there is measurable amount of RNA (from the mRNA vaccine) or free nucleotides, which increase the readings on NanoDrop. By contrast, Qubit uses

fluorometric dye for specific quantification of dsDNA, which is more specific for DNA quantification.

What is reassuring is that with both gel electrophoresis and with the Agilent 2100 bioanalyzer we found the size of the residual DNA in Pfizer mRNA vaccines is well below 100 bp.

Additionally, no replication-competent DNA was recovered from the Pfizer mRNA vaccines, although it was detected sporadically from an in-house mRNA vaccine and a biosimilar vaccine. These findings highlight the rigorousness of the commercial manufacturing process in that large pDNA templates appear to be completely cleaved into smaller pieces.

The potential health risk posed by residual small DNA fragments is currently unknown. The plasmid DNA template does not contain oncogene or any eukaryotic promoters/enhancers, it is also not known that these small DNA fragments can integrate into host DNA. Therefore, it is less likely that these DNA fragments will be oncogenic or infectious. Smaller DNA fragments can be immunostimulatory, contributing to the local reactions after vaccination. Future research is warranted to address such a concern.

Our study is limited by sample size. It is conceivable that testing more commercial mRNA vaccines will build public trust and accumulate data to set a limit for pDNA.

Figure Legends

Figure 1. A simplified workflow for mRNA vaccine production. A DNA plasmid containing the gene sequence of the SARS-CoV-2 Spike protein is linearized and used as the template for *in vitro* transcription by T7 RNA polymerase. The reaction mixture then undergoes DNase digestion to remove the original plasmid DNA. The derived mRNA is subsequently purified and encapsulated within a mixture of lipids that form lipid nanoparticles (LNP). Delivery of mRNA-LNP into human cells leads to the production of Spike protein and triggers specific immune responses.

Figure 2. A simple strategy to detect replication-competent (transformable) DNA from mRNA vaccines: isolate DNA from mRNA vaccines, ligate into a circular form, transform DNA into *E. Coli* Cells, grow on a LB plate in the presence of an antibiotic. Only those bacteria that obtain the antibiotic-resistant gene from the template plasmid DNA will form colonies in the presence of antibiotic.

Figure 3. Detection of replication-competent DNA from an in-house made mRNA vaccine. A, colony growth after transformation. B & C, colony-derived DNA is visualized on an agarose gel and then sequenced. A portion of the detected sequence from the template pDNA is shown here.

Figure 4. Detection of replication-competent DNA from biosimilar mRNA vaccines. A, gel electrophoresis images of DNA isolated from three different experimental mRNA vaccines. B, summary of DNA concentrations and the numbers of colonies after transformation. C, propagation of colonies in LB broth with antibiotics. D, gel electrophoresis images of DNA extracted from colony-derived cultures. Red star signs indicate two bands that are barely visible.

Figure 5. DNA analysis of Pfizer COVID-19 mRNA vaccines. A, six samples from two different Pfizer mRNA vaccine lots (Lot PAA194854, monovalent; PAA184098, bivalent). B, gel electrophoresis images of DNA extracted from one human dose (30 µg) of Pfizer vaccines. C, colony formation. D, high-sensitivity DNA assay by Agilent 2100 bioanalyzer. The DNA ladder contains 15 DNA fragments with indicated sizes. E, DNA size analysis on bioanalyzer. The 35- and 10380-bp DNA ladders were added to every sample as controls.

Figure 6. DNA amounts from 30 µg Pfizer mRNA vaccines measured by NanoDrop and Qubit.

Table 1. Amounts of residual DNA in Pfizer COVID-19 mRNA vaccines

Sample #	Lot	Nanodrop (ng/ μ L) ¹	Total DNA (ng) ¹	Qubit dsDNA HS assay (ng/ μ L) ²	Total dsDNA (ng) ²	Fragment Size (Agilent 2100 Bioanalyzer) ³	#colony
1	mono	69	3450	1.34	67	Peaks around 35bp, <100bp	0
2	bi	74	3700	0.968	48.4		
3	mono	131	6550	2.19	109.5		
4	bi	95	4750	1.37	68.5		
5	mono	82	4100	0.828	41.4		
6	bi	72	3600	1.34	67		

¹Nanodrop is a spectrometer that measures DNA concentration based on UV absorbance, which does not distinguish DNA or RNA. It's also easily affected by free nucleotides, salts, and organic compounds.

²Qubit uses fluorometric dye for specific quantification of dsDNA. ³Refer to Figure 5D. Monovalent (mono) vaccine contains the Wuhan variant spike protein sequence, whereas the bivalent (bi) vaccine contains both the Wuhan variant and Omicron BA.5 variant spike sequences.

Materials and Methods

This work was conducted in the BSL-1 research facility on FDA white oak campus. Tyler Wang was a participant of the 2023-2024 Student Volunteer Service Program.

MRNA vaccines. The in-house mRNA vaccine contains the SARS-CoV-2 variant XBB.1.5 spike sequence. The mRNA was *in vitro* transcribed from a pcDNA3.1(+) vector containing relevant spike sequence flanked by a 5'-UTR and 3'-UTR and was formulated with SM-102, DSPC, cholesterol, and DMG-PEG 2000 at a molar ratio of 50:10:38.5:1.5 at Cayman Chemical. The Pfizer and Moderna biosimilar COVID-19 biosimilar vaccines were obtained from BEI resources (NR-59449 and NR-59450, respectively). COMIRNATY (COVID-19 Vaccine, mRNA) BNT162b2 Original (NR-59604) and BNT162b2 Bivalent (NR-59605) were acquired from BEI resources.

DNA extraction and quantification. Residual DNA from 5 to 50 µg mRNA vaccines in the volume of 50–300 µl was extracted using Monarch Plasmid DNA Miniprep kit (New England Biolabs) following the manufacturers' instruction. The RNA component in the vaccine is presumably removed because the Neutralization Buffer (B3) in the kit contains RNase A. At the final step, 30 µl nuclease free water was added to each column for elution. Eluted DNA was quantified on a NanoDrop Microvolume Spectrophotometer or Qubit Fluorometer using the Qubit dsDNA HS Assay Kit (ThermoFisher Scientific).

Agarose gel electrophoresis. 5 μ l residual DNA was mixed with 1 μ l 6x DNA loading buffer with dye before loading to a 1% agarose gel containing TAE and GelRed Nucleic Acid Stain (Biotium). Electrophoresis was run at around 100 volts on a PowerPac Basic Power Supply (Bio-Rad) till DNA fragments were well separated on the gel. Gel images were captured under UV light in a Gel Doc system (Thermo Fisher Scientific).

Ligation and Transformation. The ligation reaction was set up at room temperature in a volume of 20 μ l consisting of 10 μ l residual DNA, 2 μ l 10x ligation buffer, 7 μ l nuclease free water, and 1 μ l T4 DNA ligase (New England Biolabs). The ligated product was transformed into DH5 α competent cells using the 5x KCM (0.5 M KCl, 0.15 M CaCl₂, and 0.25 M MgCl₂) method. In brief, 100 μ l competent cells were thawed on ice. 20 μ l ligated product was added to 20 μ l 5x KCM buffer plus 60 μ l nuclear free water and then mixed with thawed cells. After 20 minutes incubation on ice, the cells were left at room temperature for 10 minutes. 500 μ l SOC medium was added to each tube containing cells and left in a 37 °C bacterial shaker for 45 minutes at 225 rpm. Recovered cells were spread on Luria broth (LB) agars plates with 100 μ g/ml ampicillin or 50 μ g/ml kanamycin. After 16 hours incubation at 37 °C, bacterial colonies were visually inspected using a white light box.

DNA Size Analysis. 8 μ l of residual DNA isolated from Pfizer mRNA vaccines was submitted to Facility for Biotechnology Resources for size analysis on the Agilent 2100 Bioanalyzer using

the High Sensitivity DNA Assay kit (Agilent). A ladder including 15 size markers ranging from 35 to 10380 bp was included in the analysis.

Statistical analysis

Standard unpaired T Test was used to calculate statistical significance through GraphPad Prism (8.4.2) software for Windows, GraphPad Software, San Diego, California USA.

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A

Negative Control

Positive Control

Ligated Product

B

C

B

DNA Sample Origin	DNA Concentration	# Colony
1. Moderna biosimilar (5 μg)	26 ng/ μl	0
2. Pfizer biosimilar (5 μg)	16 ng/ μl	2
3. In-house mRNA (50 μg)	95 ng/ μl	0

C Colony-derived cultures

DNA Sample Origin	DNA Concentration	# Colony
1. Moderna biosimilar (5 μg)	26 $\text{ng}/\mu\text{l}$	0
2. Pfizer biosimilar (5 μg)	16 $\text{ng}/\mu\text{l}$	2
3. In-house mRNA (50 μg)	95 $\text{ng}/\mu\text{l}$	0

Colony-derived cultures

Colony #1 Colony #2

Pos Ctrl

Colony #1 Colony #2

Pos Ctrl

A

DNA (ng)/dose Pfizer vaccine

	Mono	Bi	Mono	Bi
Mean (ng)	4700	4017	72.63	61.3
Std. Dev	1635	637.1	34.4	11.2
P value	0.0023	0.0051	0.0185	0.0416

NanoDrop

Qubit